

Endovascular versus Open Surgery for Acute Mesenteric Ischemia: a systematic review

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Registration

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Authors

- Nailton Galdino de Oliveira (ORCID 0009-0000-0317-2236)
- Marcio José Cardoso Amaral (ORCID 0000-0001-7643-9958)
- Renato Nardi Pedro (ORCID 0000-0002-5447-8785)
- Bruno Zilberstein (ORCID 0000-0002-1809-8558)

Objectives

To evaluate the benefits and harms of endovascular revascularisation versus open surgical revascularisation for acute arterial mesenteric ischaemia in adult patients.

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion: Prospective and retrospective comparative cohort studies in adults (≥ 18 years) with acute arterial mesenteric ischaemia comparing endovascular with open surgical revascularisation.

Exclusion: Randomised trials, non-comparative case series/reports, chronic or venous mesenteric ischaemia, paediatric populations, conference abstracts without full data, and studies lacking extractable outcomes.

Search methods

Databases: CENTRAL, MEDLINE, Embase, Scopus, Web of Science.

Supplementary: backward reference screening, forward citation tracking, author contact.

Last search date: 8 August 2024.

Outcomes

Primary: All-cause mortality (in-hospital or ≤ 30 days).

Secondary: Bowel resection rate; second-look laparotomy; need for re-intervention; length of hospital stay; major procedure-related complications; direct hospital costs.

Risk of bias assessment

ROBINS-I tool applied to all included comparative cohort studies.

Synthesis methods

Random-effects meta-analysis (DerSimonian–Laird). Narrative SWiM synthesis where pooling is inappropriate. Certainty of evidence rated with GRADE.

Planned presentation of results

Forest plots, Summary of Findings table, and PRISMA flow diagram will be included in the final review.

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